

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic evaluation and utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

Characterizing adult plant resistance to bacterial blight (BB)

Zhang Qi and T. W. Mew, *IRRI*

1. Adult plant resistance of selected Chinese cultivars

We evaluated 30 Chinese rice cultivars for BB resistance at IRRI. Nine cultivars appeared to have adult-plant resistance. This study seeks to understand how such adult-plant resistance is expressed.

Effect of plant growth stages. The 9 cultivars were evaluated for BB resistance 21 and 45 d after sowing and at booting. Their response to the four Philippine races of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* differed with growth stage. All cultivars were very susceptible as seedlings but with age developed resistance to one or all of the races (see table). Guai Zhou Magu scores for race 1 decreased from 8.5 as seedlings to 5.5 at maximum tillering and 1.0 at booting. Kwang-er-ai 5 disease scores decreased from 7.5 as seedlings to 5.7 at maximum tillering and

2.2 at booting. Growth stage did not affect the response of Shi-zu and of susceptible check TN1 to the four races.

Reaction patterns of adult plant resistance. Among the cultivars with adult plant resistance, two disease development patterns were observed from the 6th leaf to the flag leaf. Resistance of most cultivars, such as Taichung Sen 5 and Kwang-er-ai 5, increased gradually as the leaf number increased from the 6th to flag leaves. Guai Zhou Magu, however, had a clear-cut susceptible and resistant response (Fig. 1).

Leaf response varied. Some cultivars showed resistance earlier than others. Guai Zhou Magu, Nangen 15, and Peng Chiu Mung were resistant from the 9th leaf and Taichung Sen 5 was resistant from the 11th to 12th leaf (Fig. 1). All flag leaves were BB resistant.

Six cultivars were resistant to the four races at booting stage. Wan Mi Hsiang, 3330 and Chin Kong Tao 3 were resistant only to some races at maturity (see table). □

Adult plant BB resistance of Chinese varieties at seedling, maximum tillering, and adult stages. IRRI, 1984.

Variety	Resistance ^a to given race											
	PXO 61			PXO 86			PXO 79			PXO 71		
	SS	MTS	BS	SS	MTS	BS	SS	MTS	BS	SS	MTS	BS
Guai Zhou Magu	8.5	5.5	1.0	8.5	3.1	1.1	8.0	5.2	1.0	7.0	5.0	1.4
Nangen 11	6.5	4.0	1.0	6.3	3.0	1.0	6.5	3.3	1.0	6.0	3.5	1.0
Peng Chiu Mung	6.5	3.1	1.2	6.1	1.3	1.0	6.0	3.0	1.0	6.2	3.2	1.0
Nangen 15	6.7	5.5	2.0	6.5	3.0	1.7	6.5	5.6	2.8	7.0	5.1	1.0
Kwang-er-ai 5	8.5	6.2	2.7	6.5	5.0	1.5	9.0	7.0	2.7	9.0	7.0	2.8
Taichung Sen 5	7.0	4.7	3.0	7.5	4.7	2.0	9.0	5.4	3.0	8.0	4.3	3.0
3330	7.5	5.7	3.5	6.7	3.3	1.6	7.2	5.4	2.7	7.2	5.5	4.0
Chin Kong Tao ³	7.0	4.3	3.5	6.7	3.7	1.7	6.7	4.8	1.2	7.3	6.6	6.8
Wan Mi Hsiang	9	5.4	4.7	7	3.0	1.3	8.5	5.0	5.0	9	6	5.0
Shi-zu	1.0	1.3	1.0	3.0	1.0	1.0	2.5	1.3	1.0	1.0	1.2	1.0
IR1545-339	1.8	3.0	1.0	3.5	3.0	1.0	3.2	2.0	1.0	6.8	5.0	6.0
TN1	9	8.0	6.8	9	6.7	4.3	9	7.3	6.3	9	7.3	7.0

^aBy the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale. SS = seedling stage, MTS = maximum tillering stage, BS = booting stage.

Disease scale

Disease scale

1. Reactions of 3 rices to the 4 BB races from 6th to flag leaf. IRRI, 1984.

2. Greenhouse testing of *Xa 6* and *Xa 3* genes for BB resistance

Rices with adult plant disease resistance are disease susceptible as seedlings and develop resistance as they mature.

Zenith, Malagkit Sungsong, and lines IR1695 and IR944 derived respectively from them have the *Xa 6* gene for BB resistance. Wase Aikoku 3 has the *Xa 3*

Disease scale

Leaf position

gene. We evaluated the rice for resistance expression in the IRRI greenhouse.

Four BB races were inoculated 4-5 times at the 6th to flag leaf of the same plants. TN1, the susceptible check, was susceptible to the four races at all leaf positions (Fig. 2).

IR1545-339, a line with differential BB resistance, was resistant to races 1, 2, and 3 and susceptible to race 4 at all leaf positions. Zenith was resistant from the 11th to the flag leaf, and IR1695 developed BB similarly. M. Sungsong was resistant from the 9th leaf and IR944, from the 12th leaf.

When planting order was staggered to synchronize inoculation of different leaf positions, Zenith and M. Sungsong developed resistance to the 4 races at similar leaf positions (Fig. 3).

Wase Aikoku 3 had adult plant resistance only to races 1, 2, 4, and was resistant to race 3 at all leaf positions (Fig. 2). □

Disease scale

3. Reactions of Zenith and Malagkit Sungsong inoculated with 4 BB races at the same time. IRRI, 1984.

3. Influence of temperature on the *Xa 6* gene for BB adult plant resistance

High temperature favors BB development, but it is not known whether adult plant resistance controlled by the *Xa 6* gene is stable in high temperature.

2. Reactions of Wase Aikoku 3 and TN1 inoculated with 4 BB races at the same time. IRRI, 1984.

We evaluated BB resistance of Zenith, M. Sungsong, IR1695, and IR944 at 33-25, 29-21, and 25-20°C ranges in growth chambers with 70% relative humidity. The four cultivars have the *Xa 6* gene.

Zenith and M. Sungsong resistance was unaffected by temperature changes. However, resistance by leaf position was not consistent with greenhouse observations. Zenith and M. Sungsong expressed resistance best at booting stage (Fig. 4, 5). Lesions developed slowly, gradually yellowed, and stopped growing. The cultivars showed resistance earlier at 25-20°C than at 29-21°C.

Temperature affected BB development more in IR1695 and IR944. At higher temperatures, lesions were longer than those of their parents, but the difference was insignificant at booting. Temperature did not affect TN1 lesion development. □

4. Bacteriophage method for estimating *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* multiplication in infected rice leaves

Taking direct counts of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* cells by plating on ordinary media is impossible because the bacterium is slow growing and subject to contamination, especially in the tropics. We tested the bacteriophage method for estimating bacterial multiplication on rice leaf tissue.

A suitable bacterial strain and a phage strain were selected and a one-step growth experiment was done to characterize the phage-bacterium relationship. A titration curve of the bacteria densities with the phage also was established for reference. The estimate was based on plaque-forming units (Pfu) caused by infection of the bacterial cells by the phage particles. We used a titration curve based on a serial dilution of isolate PXO 61 of BB pathogen in response to phage strain P-80 (Fig. 6).

To estimate multiplication in Zenith leaves, six 5-cm-long led samples infected with PXO 61 were observed at different times after inoculation. The samples were disinfected with 70% ethanol and rinsed several times in sterile distilled water. The leaf specimens were homogenized in 5-ml filter-sterilized PSB medium. The leaf extract was diluted serially. For a viability count, 0.1 ml of the extract was

4. Disease reactions of Zenith to BB races at 3 temperature ranges. IRRI, 1984.

5. Disease reactions of Malagkit Sungsong to the 4 BB races at 3 temperature ranges. IRRI, 1984.

6. The titration curve of bacterial density with a standard phage concentration. IRRI, 1984.

7. Relationship between phage count (PFu/cm²) and colony (CFu/cm²) at different leaf positions of Zenith with BB lesions. IRRI, 1984.

plated on PSA medium. The rest was mixed with a standard phage concentration.

Ten minutes after incubation at 28°C in aeration, the mixture was centrifuged

to remove the excess phage. The precipitate was resuspended and incubated for 20 min to estimate phage absorption by the bacterial cells. Final phage plating was 10 h after incubation. The correlation between viability count for bacteria and phage count as an indication of bacterial multiplication is shown in

Figure 7. The bacteriophage method seems reliable and efficient for detecting bacterial multiplication in Pfu larger than $10^3/\text{ml}$. □

5. Relation of lesion development and bacterial multiplication in different leaf positions of Zenith inoculated with *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*

Zenith, with *Xa 6* gene for BB resistance, shows resistance from the 11th leaf. It is unclear if bacterial multiplication in susceptible and resistant leaf positions varies. We investigated bacterial multiplication in the 6th, 9th, 10th, and 12th

leaf positions on Zenith using the bacteriophage method.

Six samples from each leaf position were examined at 1, 24, 48, 72, and 158 h after inoculation (HAI). Lesion development was measured at the same time.

On the susceptible 6th, 9th, and 10th leaf positions, lesions began to develop 48 HAI and grew very fast. On the 12th leaf, the lesions were visible 96 HAI, and developed slowly. Two weeks after inoculation, lesion length was 23.6, 18.2, 16.4, and 2.4 cm on leaves 6, 9, 10, and 12 respectively (Fig. 8).

The phage count, expressed as plaque-forming units/cm² leaf area, on leaves 6, 9, and 10 increased 24 HAI, indirectly

indicating bacterial multiplication. Phage count at 48 HAI increased very fast. It peaked at 72 h, then slightly declined. Leaf tissue was totally infected at 120 and 158 h. The phage count on leaf 12 also increased 48 HAI, but was less than on other leaves and declined faster (Fig. 9). □

8. BB lesion development on different leaf positions of Zenith in the greenhouse. IIRI, 1984.

9. Multiplication of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* on leaves 6, 9, 10, and 12 of Zenith estimated by the phage method. IIRI, 1984.

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN.

Performance of HKR101 under bacterial blight (BB) stress

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HKR101 is a medium-duration semidwarf rice with long bold grains. It was developed at HAU Rice Research Station. We evaluated artificially inoculated HKR101 for BB resistance in a replicated trial from 1980 to 1983. Check varieties were Jaya and PR106.

Whole plots were inoculated 30 d after transplanting by cutting 5 cm from leaf tops with a sickle dipped in inoculum. Inoculum was prepared by soaking 1-cm pieces of infected leaves for 20 min. Al-

though HKR101 was as susceptible to BB as the check varieties, it yielded 16% more (see table). HKR101 has better grain quality than Jaya or PR106, and equal milling recovery. □

Performance of HKR101 under BB stress, Haryana, India.

Variety	BB reaction ^a	Yield (t/ha)					Duration (d)	Panicles/m ²	Kernel length (mm)	Kernel breadth (mm)	Length-breadth ratio	Milling recovery (%)
		1980	1981	1982	1983	Mean						
HKR101	9	5.0	6.0	4.9	3.7	4.9	144	306	7.3	2.5	2.9	66
Jaya	9	4.4	4.9	4.1	3.2	4.2	146	281	6.6	2.6	2.6	66
PR106	9	4.3	5.1	4.4	3.0	4.2	147	292	7.1	2.1	3.4	66
CD at 5%		.8	.9	1.1	.4							
CV %		11.12	10.7	15.97	7.03							

^aIIRI Standard Evaluation System for Rice.